

FIND MARRIAGE TIMING BY JUPITER TRANSIT WITH SEVENTH HOUSE LORD

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Abstract:

Astrology is the divine profession. Astrologers are worshipped by their clients as God. The perfect prediction gives name and fame to the astrologers. Timing of the event finding is very important to attract our clients. It gives not only name and fame but also huge money.

Key Words: Astrology - Prediction - Know the Future - Accuracy - Name And Fame - Also Money - To Astrologer - Customer Happy - Good Karma.

Methods to Find the Timing of the Event:

There are so many methods followed by astrologers to calculate the timing of the event. They are traditional astrology, K.P astrology, Brigu Nandi Nadi astrology, Jamakkol astrology, Horary, Mundane astrology and Jamini astrology.

Some Important Events:

- When will one get marriage?
- When will one get child?
- When will one construct the house?
- When will one go to abroad?
- When will one get Job?
- When will one win in court case?
- When will one recover from sick?
- When will one win his / her enemies?
- When will one buy a vehicle?
- When will one get divorce?
- When will one get remarriage?
- When will one get loan?
- When will one get treasure?
- When will one close his / her loan?
- When will one go to pilgrimage?
- When will one do adoption?
- When will one get promotion?
- When will one get reward?
- When will one die?
- When will one meet accident?
- When will one expand his business?
- When will one attain divine power?
- When will one shine in life?
- When will one enjoy the life?
- When will one get bail?

In this article we focus the timing of marriage.

How to Find out the Timing of Marriage?

There are so many methods to find out the timing of marriage. I have followed two methods to find out the timing of marriage.

Method 1:

In horoscope we can note the seventh house lord from rasi chart (D1). Then we note the sign where the Seventh lord stands in Navamsa chart (D9). Then the transit Jupiter aspects or conjunctions with the Navamsa sign where the seventh house lord stands. It is the auspicious time for marriage.

Method 2:

In horoscope the transit Jupiter aspects the ascendent or the moon sign It is the auspicious time for marriage.

In this article we have seen some examples for method 1

Example Charts:

Timing of Marriage the role of transit Jupiter with Seventh house Lord:

Example Horoscope 1:

Gender	:	Male
Date of birth	:	04.11.1953
Time of birth	:	09.30 am.
Place of birth	:	Tuticorin
Wedding date	:	22.05.1977
Ascendent	:	Sagittarius
Seventh house lord	:	Mercury
Seventh house lord Standing Navamsa Sign	:	Virgo
Transit Jupiter stood at the time of marriage	:	Taurus
Aspect of Jupiter to seventh lord	:	Fifth

4	5	6	Jupiter
3	RASI Star : Hastha 3		Kethu
Rahu			9
ASC	Merc	Sun Sat	Mars Moon Venus

Mars Sun	12	ASC	Moon
10	NAVAMSA		3
9			Kethu
Sat	7	Jupiter	Venus Merc

Moon dasa balance 2 years 8 Months 16 days

In this horoscope the Seventh lord Mercury stands in Virgo sign in Navamsa. The transit Jupiter stands in Taurus and aspects by fifth

Example Horoscope 2:

Gender	:	Female
Date of birth	:	04.03.1978
Time of birth	:	05.39 am.
Place of birth	:	Tuticorin
Wedding date	:	15.11.2002
Ascendent	:	Aquaris
Seventh house lord	:	Sun
Seventh house lord Standing Navamsa Sign	:	Pisces
Transit Jupiter stood at the time of marriage	:	Cancer
Aspect of Jupiter to seventh lord	:	Nineth

Kethu	3	4	Jupiter Mars
ASC Venus Merc Sun	RASI Star : Moolam 4		6
12			Saturn
Moon	10	9	Rahu

Sun	Satum	Rahu Merc	Mars Venus
4	NAVAMSA		Moon
3			10
2	ASC Kethu	Jupiter	11

Kethu dasa balance 1 year 0 months 16 days

In this horoscope the Seventh lord Sun stands in Pisces sign in Navamsa. The transit Jupiter stands in Cancer and aspects by ninth

Example Horoscope 3:

Gender	:	Male
Date of birth	:	24.09.1976
Time of birth	:	07.14 pm.
Place of birth	:	Theni
Wedding date	:	15.11.2002
Ascendent	:	Pisces
Seventh house lord	:	Mercury
Seventh house lord Standing Navamsa Sign	:	Capricorn
Transit Jupiter stood at the time of marriage	:	Cancer
Aspect of Jupiter to seventh lord	:	Seventh

ASC	Kethu	Jupiter	4
12	RASI Star : Hastha 3		Saturn
11			6
10	9	Rahu Venus	Merc Moon, Sun Mars

Sun Jupiter	3	4	Moon
ASC	NAVAMSA		Kethu
Merc Rahu			7
Saturn	Venus	9	Mars

Moon Dasa balance 3 years 7 months 23 days

In this horoscope the Seventh lord Mercury stands in Capricorn sign in Navamsa. The transit Jupiter stands in Cancer and aspects by seventh

Example Horoscope 4:

Gender	:	Female
Date of birth	:	02.09.1999
Time of birth	:	04.00 pm.
Place of birth	:	Chennai
Wedding date	:	11.09.2019
Ascendent	:	Capricorn
Seventh house lord	:	Moon
Seventh house lord Standing Navamsa Sign	:	Pisces
Transit Jupiter stood at the time of marriage	:	Scorpio
Aspect of Jupiter to seventh lord	:	Fifth

3	Jupiter Sat	Moon	6
2	RASI Star : Krithigai 4		Rahu Venus
ASC Kethu			Merc Sun
12	Mars	10	9

ASC Moon	2	3	Kethu Merc
Venus	NAVAMSA		Jupiter
11			Sun Mars
Rahu	9	Saturn	7

Sun dasa balance 0 years 4 months 16 days

In this horoscope the Seventh lord Moon stands in Piscus sign in Navamsa. The transit Jupiter stands in Scorpio and aspects by fifth.

Example Horoscope 5:

Gender	:	Female
Date of birth	:	09.04.1994
Time of birth	:	03.00 pm.
Place of birth	:	Chennai
Wedding date	:	14.02.2021
Ascendent	:	Leo
Seventh house lord	:	Saturn
Seventh house lord Standing Navamsa Sign	:	Aquaris
Transit Jupiter stood at the time of marriage	:	Aquaris
Aspect of Jupiter to seventh lord	:	Conjunction

Sun Moon Merc Mars	Venus	Kethu	11
Saturn	RASI Star : Uthratathi 2		12
6			ASC
5	Rahu	Jupiter	2

Jupiter	11	12	ASC
Sun Sat	NAVAMSA		Mars Rahu
Kethu			Venus Merc
7	6	5	Moon

Saturn dasa balance 12 years 6 months 4 days

In this horoscope the Seventh lord Saturn stands in Aquaris sign in Navamsa. The transit Jupiter stands in Aquaris and conjunction with Saturn.

Example Horoscope 6:

Gender	:	Female
Date of birth	:	20.01.1985
Time of birth	:	02.55 pm.
Place of birth	:	Madurai
Wedding date	:	01.09.2004
Ascendent	:	Taurus
Seventh house lord	:	Mars

Seventh house lord Standing Navamsa Sign : Taurus
 Transit Jupiter stood at the time of marriage : Virgo
 Aspect of Jupiter to seventh lord : Nineth

11	12	ASC Rahu	2
Mars Venus	RASI Star:Uthradam 1		3
Sun Jupiter			4
Moon Merc	Kethu Saturn	6	5

9	10	Venus Mars	12
Sun	NAVAMSA		ASC Kethu Sat
Jupiter Rahu			2
Moon	5	4	Merc

Sun dasa balance 05 years 04 months 19 days

In this horoscope the Seventh lord Mercury stands in Virgo sign in Navamsa. The transit Jupiter stands in Taurus and aspects by fifth.

Conclusion:

From above examples we have easily find out the timing of marriage. It helps our customer to do the preparation for marriage. If we say the particular period of marriage, our customers will be happy.

References:

1. Jathaga Alangaram - Moolamum Uraiyum - written by Keeranur Natarajan, Sri Indhu Publications, Chennai 600 0035, 2017.
2. Thirumana Kala Nirnayam written by Santhalinganaar Thiruvarul Jothida Payirchi Maiyam
3. Sagotharan, Vasathi, Thirumanam tharum yogangal written by Prof. S. P. Subramanian L.C.E, Sri Devi Puthaga Nilayam, Chennai 600 003, 2017
4. Kudumba Jothida Kalanjiyam edited by Prof. S. P. Subramanian L.C.E, Tirumagal Nilayam, 2017
5. M. K. University Prof. Dr. K. R. Subramanian
6. Annamalai University Prof. Dr. K.R. Subramanian